

Preliminary market research on the market acceptance of the electric boat, the possibilities of its sale, the development of the distribution price and the expected production volume depending on market needs.

Within the framework of its R&D tender, the applicant Beocia Kft. Set the goal of creating a ship of a kind that

makes it available. The aim is to increase the number of users currently active in the small craft market by keeping the selling price of the finished product low, thus

During the market positioning of the new product, Beocia Kft. Is thinking about the development of a business and price policy aimed at the masses.

I. The aim, aspects, means of the aim of the research:

The aim of our research:

The basic aim of our research was to assess the approximate number and needs of Hungarian watercraft users, the age and type composition of the fleet (petrol and electric propulsion), and to get an idea of how the market would respond to a two-hull model to be introduced by Beocia Kft. electric watercraft.

We can use our questionnaire to find out the shipowners

- are open to a new technology
- how many would buy an electric vehicle
- how much money would be spent on an e-ship
- primarily for what purpose
- what are their performance expectations
- What are your expectations for a modern e-ship?

How to do our research:

- In Hungary, approximately 20-22 thousand boats ring on the water or are waiting to be launched in the season. Of course, our survey could not reach all Hungarian shipowners, but our survey based on a sampling group of almost 6,000 people is representative, because although most of the boat users we use use their craft for recreational purposes, the responding boaters use several water types (river, lake, mine, backwater, etc.) use its ship, the performance of the craft varies over an extremely wide range, and all the major materials are included in the hull components.

- It is fortunate that a large number of respondents, more than eight hundred, have classified themselves as professional or professional shipowners who use their craft for their daily work (in many cases, of course, a boat is used by several people).

Aspects of our research:

The most important question that our survey wanted to answer was how our preliminary market research assessed the reception of the electric vessel, how sales data could develop in the future, at what commercial prices it could be sold, and in what quantities it could be demanded by customers.

The aim of our market research was to get the answers to the questions asked by the customer Beocia Kft. From future customers and users. As a first step, we tried to assess applicability with our comprehensive questions.

At the beginning of our work, we were confident that the answers to our questions would help Beocia Ltd. to establish the customer base to be formed in the future and to determine the future commercial selling price.

We also tried to assess which potential sales groups or channels could be that could generate the most positive sales data possible.

The larger group in our survey consisted of the leisure hiker and angler group, but the number of professional users was also opinion-forming.

Tools of our research:

Primarily online

- The survey was mostly implemented online (questionnaires, social media), but in many cases we interviewed during a field visit and also conducted a group survey in a forum.

II. Results, findings

After evaluating the online questionnaires received and the public data available to us, we were able to establish the following results:

Nowadays approx. 20-22 thousand use a more or less regular, registered conventional explosive-powered watercraft. Once the operation of explosive-propelled vessels is subject to registration only above a certain engine power, the number of unreported motor vehicles may be three times that.

Approximately 800-900 people use a declared electric device for waterborne transport, but the number of unreported electric drives can reach 6-7 times that. Given the electric propulsion of the vessel to be developed, the number of users of the operating principle is exceptionally high, which increases the number of sailors interested in the future vessel.

74 percent of our sample of nearly 6,000 people said they would be open to a new electronic technology.

The following general findings can be drawn from the responses to the online surveys:

- The average user has approx. spend three to four weeks on or near water
- Spends 6-8 M HUF to buy a boat

- It allocates HUF 6-800 thousand per year for the storage, maintenance and servicing of the ship
- 4.7 percent of respondents admitted to buying a more powerful boat primarily for reasons of prestige. They see a higher prestige value in an e-boat, even if its equipment and style are dominated by uses rather than luxury design.

Forty percent of respondents self-report that they usually do not, or even more never, take advantage of the size and performance of their craft.

More than 15 percent of respondents have repeatedly failed to launch their boat all year round, and its purchase was more for prestige purposes.

Approximately 26 percent of respondents are skeptical, either do not trust the new electrical technology, or believe that it is not beneficial for the usability of this type of vessel. The doubt stems primarily from the compulsion of low uptime and low power.

Where would they be used?

Although the new model should not fit in the same places as the existing watercraft fleet, ie in the rivers of the Danube, Tisza, Drava, Körös, the possibilities of use are finite. The motorization of the completed vessel is not suitable for overcoming the power of flowing water, so their usability is limited to stagnant or running at minimum speed.

It is an advantage that there was an increased interest among the sailors in the protected waters (Lake Balaton, Lake Velence, Lake Tisza) for an understandable reason. Commercial utilization may dominate here, companies dealing with excursions, passenger transport and chartering have a huge potential, the low operating costs, low draft and modularity of the ship can be very favorable for them. Given their low cost, direct sales may be the ideal strategy for finding them.

There is even more interest among anglers, who pursue their passion primarily in waters closed to gasoline engines, travel shorter distances, but also spend more time on the water.

Many liked the reduction in the draft of the ship to be built compared to the average. A recurring problem among lake sailors is the relatively greater dive depth, which can cause near-shore traffic.

Especially for those sailing on Lake Balaton, there was a recurring question, the operating time of the batteries that drive the ship's electric motor, whether the ship could be suitable for crossing the lake.

Who would use it?

The target group of the e-ship buyer to be introduced would more or less cover the current market target group. The difference may be the higher number of professional sailors. According to our survey, the greatest interest may be shown by companies working in companies. There is a clear interest from conservation groups in scientific work, who appreciate the hull, which can accommodate more space, the possibility of more flexible space design, the versatility of modularity and the large work surface.

In this connection, special needs have been indicated, for example, in the case of national park conservation guards in protected waters, cartographic, water, biological work may be available for the new boat, but several also mentioned .

New customers

Due to the length and electric propulsion of the ship to be developed, it does not require official registration and a driver's license, some respondents said that in the future their friends among their family members may also be attractive to those who have not been sailing before. All this can strengthen the widespread use of the e-ship.

Environmental awareness and related expectations:

Surprisingly, almost 90 percent of those surveyed said they support the proliferation of e-ships in terms of environmental protection, even if they may face a reduction in performance over gasoline engines.

Ship design, material and resource performance

It was particularly striking among professional users that, instead of the luxury design of ships in this category, the emphasis was on usability in terms of expectations. In contrast to wood coverings and more expensive materials, the use of durable, well-cleanable materials was suggested, the main aspect being the durable court.

In terms of equipment, the ship's toilet is important, but instead of the sink, I would rather see the expansion of the storage compartments, the increased area of the free loading space.

Approximately 44 percent of respondents would insist that, in addition to the electric motor, a conventional explosive motor be placed on the hull in parallel, at least optionally.

There seems to be a clear expectation on the part of the new ship from almost all respondents to be able to charge the batteries not only with the help of solar panels, but also with the option of plug-in charging. Moreover, they can quickly and easily switch to conventional engine use when needed.

In light of the numbers, it is expected that a minimum of 4-6 hours of operating time can be expected for charged batteries, even if this is supplemented by on-the-go solar charging.

Among the non-professional users, the possibility of installing consumer electronics and the possibility of installing the necessary receiving device connections emerged as a recurring requirement.

In addition to some distrustful respondents, the majority welcomed the idea of designing a catamaran body because lower friction, more moderate water and air resistance also mean higher performance and more stable water grip.

It didn't come up as an issue, so we dare say that the hull material was welcomed: the already proven uv-resistant gelcoat, and the much-anticipated cake technology sheet structure.

A recurring issue and a clear need, the design of a roof and / or awning to provide protection from the weather, has been signaled by almost everyone.

More than two-thirds of non-professional users expressed the need to design a sleeping and toilet space.

III. Establishing the market price of a new electric vessel

In the light of the figures, the original idea of Beocia Kft., According to which a completely new type of ship category would be created and introduced to the domestic market, seems justified. After all, the development will make it possible to create a vessel that better meets the needs of the freshwater shipping population in Central and Eastern Europe than the existing range, but this must be possible at a lower cost.

According to the developers, the emphasis is on functionality, which is the basis for the design of the category. But an important consideration is to consider price-sensitive customers. The price reduction should be an advantage even at the expense of amenities, leaving, of course, the possibility for anyone to increase the list of extras to order to the extreme if required.

Drive in the future

Experience has shown that a newly purchased boat is kept for at least 6-8 years by its first owner. During this time, you want to experience the low operating costs you expect at the time of sale. At the same time, the rapid development of batteries, the expected increasingly cheaper manufacturing technology, can quickly obsolete the existing design in terms of operating cost. An advantageous feature may be the cheap replacement of the batteries that ensure the operation of the ship, which does not affect the operation and operational safety, when new types available later are placed on the market. (Eg using lithium batteries.)

Other topics:

Forming an opinion based on past experience in the automotive industry, batteries now and in the future.

The design and manufacture of a ship, its entry into the market is a longer process, so it must be marketable further, e.g. for a car. Either a "time-resistant" design must be created, both in terms of aesthetics and functionality, or it must be capable of applying the intermediate level of technology. e.g. replacement of new batteries, resulting in lower production and sales prices.